

Space Time Pattern Analysis of Covid-19 Epidemics at District level in Uttar Pradesh, India

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Abstract

The general objective of this study is to study covid - 19 – epidemic at district level in Uttar Pradesh, India during 1st May 2020 to 1st June 2021. During this period of thirteen months the disastrous second wave was started from 1st April 2021. To meet the general objective, two specific objectives were set as first to study space time pattern of confirmed and deceased cases and second to model deceased cases in terms of its relationships to confirmed COVID19 cases in India API dataset was used for conformed and deceased Cases at district level in Uttar Pradesh. To visualise & analyse the space time pattern of COVID - 19 cases, space time cube was created of spatiotemporal Covid data. Thereafter statistically significant emerging hot spots trends over time were identified using space time cube as input. To model spatially varying relationships total no of deceased cases were given as dependent variable and total number of confirmed cases were set as Explanatory Variables. Spatial Autocorrelation (Morans I) statistics was used to measure spatial patterns of residuals. The overall increasing trend direction was obtained from space time cube for conformed cases (trend statistics = 4.6, Trend p-value = 0.000) and for deceased cases (trend statistics = 4.7, Trend p-value = 0.000). Three types of Hotspots were obtained for Confirmed Cases. Fourteen Hexagonal Locations covering 22 districts were obtained as New Hot Spots. Eight Hexagonal Locations covering 12 districts were obtained as Consecutive Hot Spots. Rest thirty four Hexagonal Locations covering 41 districts were obtained as statistically insignificant Hot Spots. Similarly, three types of Hotspots were obtained for deceased Cases. Eight Hexagonal Locations covering 11 districts were obtained as New Hot Spots. Seven Hexagonal Locations covering 10 districts were obtained as Consecutive Hot Spots. Rest forty one Hexagonal Locations covering 54 districts were obtained as statistically insignificant Hot Spots. The results of the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) linear regression show the strong positive relationship in between both the variables. There were 11 districts below - 0.5 Std. Dev (standard deviation) and 11 districts above + 0.5 Std. Deviation. The results of Probability ($p < 0.01$) and Robust Probability ($p < 0.01$) indicate coefficient is statistically significant. Spatial pattern of the residuals with p-value (0.037097) is statistically significant, and the z-score (2.084691) is positive. So, spatial distribution of residual's high values and/or low values in the dataset is more spatially clustered. Results indicate the districts in central part of the Uttar Pradesh got successive high no. of corona – 19 confirmed cases and deceased cases. In case of conformed cases the districts of western and eastern Uttar Pradesh have new hot spots but in case of deceased cases only eastern part of Uttar Pradesh has been affected more.

Keywords: Underground Water Level, Spatial Autocorrelation, Geographically Weighted Regression, Morans I and Geostatistical Analysis.

Introduction

India, which has the second-largest population in the world, is suffering severely from COVID-19 disease (Ghosh, Nundy, & Mallick,

2020). In India, 100,340 confirmed cases and 3155 confirmed deaths due to COVID-19 were reported as of May 18, 2020 (Sarkar, Khajanchi, & Nieto, 2020). Now Coronavirus

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Cases 29,359,155 and 367,097 confirmed deaths due to COVID-19 were reported as of May 18, 2020 (Worldometers, 2021). India's COVID-19 case tally exceeded 2.89 crore with 1,00,636 new cases reported, as per the health ministry's June 7 update. Globally, more than 17.40 crore COVID-19 cases have been recorded with 37.44 lakh deaths to 07th June 2021. Over 1.29 crore active cases have been reported across the world as on date with the US accounting for the most (42 percent), followed by India (11 percent) (Moneycontrol, 2021). Uttar Pradesh on 10th June recorded its highest daily increase in coronavirus numbers with 61 more deaths and 4,586 fresh infections. So far, 1,08,974 cases, including 1,918 fatalities, have been reported from the state (Firstpost, 2020).

Researchers in India are now trying to pinpoint what is behind the unprecedented surge, which could be due to an unfortunate confluence of factors, including the emergence of particularly infectious variants, a rise in unrestricted social interactions, and low vaccine coverage. Untangling the causes could be helpful to governments trying to suppress or prevent similar surges around the world (Mallapaty, 2021).

Geospatial techniques have been used by various scholars to study the spatial-temporal pattern of the virus spread. Geographical characteristics of those infected by COVID-19 were studied by Guan et al. (2020). Huang et al. (2020) studied Spatiotemporal analysis of COVID-19 and its relationship with epidemiological characteristics, control of measures taken and their effects. Zhou et al. (2020) performed on the data mining and confirmed cases reflections on the use of GIS with big data and spatiotemporal analysis of COVID-19. Pearson's correlation methods for spatiotemporal analysis was done by Xiong et al. (2020). Prospective space-time statistics to identify active and emerging COVID-19 groups at the county level was studied by Desjardins et al. (2020). Prediction of the global spread of COVID-19 based on geographic and climatic data was done by De Angel Sola et al.

(2020). Ma et al. (2020) performed correlation between deaths from COVID-19 in Wuhan and climate data and environmental pollution. Correlation between climate and COVID-19 in 30 Chinese cities was done by Liu et al. (2020). Correlation between climate and COVID-19 in temperate and tropical countries was done by Hasan and Mahfujul Haque (2020).

The problem of corona – 19 epidemics in Uttar Pradesh has been studied by many geospatial scholars. Tiwari et al. (2020) concluded mobility of individuals and their physical social networks are the root causes for the spread of current coronavirus pandemic in Uttar Pradesh. They propose a method of visualizing the spatial and chronological aspects of the spread of this virus based on geographical information systems (GIS) and Gephi graphs.

There are many tools available in Arc GIS for cluster analysis include Spatially Constrained Multivariate Clustering, Multivariate Clustering, Density-Based Clustering, Image Segmentation, Hot Spot Analysis, Cluster and Outlier Analysis tools, and the Space Time Pattern Mining tools (Bennett, 2018).

Space-time cubes and spatial statistics were used by Abad & Orellana (2017) to detect and characterize spatiotemporal patterns on volunteered cycling geo-information. These techniques have proven useful for exploring and analyzing cycling mobility patterns in the city of Cuenca and can be used in other intermediate cities and even larger urban areas. To find the spatial temporal pattern of covid-19 at district level in the study area, Space Time Pattern Mining tools was used.

The Space Time Pattern Mining toolbox contains statistical tools for analyzing data distributions and patterns in the context of both space and time. It includes a toolset that can be helpful for visualizing the data stored in the space-time net CDF cube in both 2D and 3D and filling missing values in your data prior to cube creation (Arc GIS, 2021).

To study spatial analysis two regression analysis tools are available first is Ordinary Least Squares Regression and another is

Geographically Weighted Regression. In this study Ordinary Least Squares Regression tool was used.

In regression models where the cases are geographical locations, sometimes regression coefficients do not remain fixed over space. A technique for exploring this phenomenon, geographically weighted regression is introduced (Brunsdon, Fotheringham, & Charlton, 1998).

Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) is the best known technique and a good starting point for all spatial regression analyses. Global model provides 1 equation to represent the entire dataset Geographically (Murack, 2021). So in the present study Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) technique was employed to study deceased cases variation in relation with confirmed cases at district level in Uttar Pradesh.

It was significant to study because, the same topic has not been studied widely by geospatial experts using space time cube analysis. The

findings of the work will help the policy makers to develop the programmes to minimise the spread of Covid-19 and to minimise the deceased rate in hard hit districts by providing infrastructure in the health centres.

The Study Area

Uttar Pradesh, the most populous and fourth largest state of India. It lies in the north-central part of the country (Mathur, 2020). Uttar Pradesh regional state of India was chosen as a study area, it extends between latitudes 23°51'30.454"N and 30°24'44.389"N and longitudes 77°9'14.694"E and 84°39'28.416"E(Fig. 1).It with a total area of 243,290 square kilometres is India's fourth-largest state in terms of land area. Uttar Pradesh with a population of more than 166 million holds distinction of being the most populous state in the country followed by Maharastra (97 million) and Bihar (83 million). (“Census of India” 2021).

Fig. 1: The Study Area

Data Base & Methodology

Information on district boundaries was collected from official website of Indian Geo Platform of IISRO, National Remote Sensing Center, Government of India (https://bhuvan.nrsc.gov.in/bhuvan_links.php) (“ISRO,” 2021).

For Covid - 19 Data, the CSV dataset for the duration from April 01st2020to May 31st 2021 was collected from Statistical web portal, Government of India, (<https://www.mygov.in/covid-19>) and from COVID19-India API. The data contains everyday number of confirmed, recovered, deceased and tested cases at district level in India (“COVID-19,” 2020).

Fig. 2: The Flowchart of the used Methodology in the Study Area

Space time cube function was used to examine time-series trends across the study area. The space time cube has aggregated 29463 points into 143 hexagon grid locations over 13 time step intervals. Each location has a height of 67046 meters, a width of 77418.05 meters, sides of 38709.03 meters, and an area of 3892928050.69 square meters. The entire space time cube spans an area 774180.52

meters west to east and 737506 meters north to south. Each of the time step intervals is 1 month in duration so the entire time period covered by the space time cube is 13 months. Of the 143 total locations, 56 (39.16%) contain at least one point for at least one time step interval. These 56 locations comprise 728 space time bins of which 728 (100.00%) have point counts greater than zero. The time extent

covers from 2020-04-26 to 2021-05-25. The option for Time step alignment was chosen as End. The First time step interval after 2020-04-25 to on or before 2020-05-25. The Last time step interval after 2021-04-25 to on or before 2021-05-25.

Emerging Hotspot analysis

Emerging Hot Spot Analysis function was used to identify trends in the clustering of point densities (counts) or summary fields in a space-time cube created by means of the Create Space Time Cube tool. Categories include new, consecutive, intensifying, persistent, diminishing, sporadic, oscillating, and historical hot and cold spots. This tool can only accept net CDF files created by the Create Space Time Cube tool. This tool analyzes a variable in the net CDF Input Space Time Cube using a space-time implementation of the Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic.

The Getis-Ord local statistics is given as follows:

$$G_i^* = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n w_{i,j} x_j - \bar{X} \sum_{j=1}^n w_{i,j}}{\sqrt{\frac{n \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij}^2 - (\sum_{j=1}^n w_{i,j})^2}{n-1}}} \quad (1)$$

Where x_j is the attribute value for feature j . w_{ij} is the spatial weight between feature i and j . n is equal to the total number of features and:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n x_j}{n} \quad (2)$$

$$z_i = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij}^2}{n}} - (\bar{X})^2 \quad (3)$$

Getis-Ord statistic is a z-score so no further calculations are required.

Modelling Spatial Relationship

Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) tool was used to model deceased cases (Dependent variable) in terms of its relationship to confirmed cases (Independent variable). The mean monthly average of both the variable was chosen from April 2020 to May 2021.

$$y = \beta + \beta x + \varepsilon \quad (4)$$

Where y is the Dependent variable, x is the Independent/Explanatory variables, β is the Regression coefficients (β) & ε is the Residuals/random error.

Spatial Autocorrelation (Moran's I) Tool was used to the spatial pattern of the residuals.

The Moran's I statistic for spatial autocorrelation is given as Eq.5:

$$I = \frac{n \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w_{i,j} z_i z_j}{S_0 \sum_{i=1}^n z_i^2} \quad (5)$$

Where, z_i is the deviation of an attribute for feature from its mean ($x_i - \bar{X}$), w_{ij} is the spatial weight between feature i and j , n is equal to the total number of features, and S_0 is the aggregate of all the spatial weights:

$$S_0 = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w_{i,j} \quad (6)$$

The z_i -score for the statistic is computed as:

$$z_I = \frac{I - E[I]}{\sqrt{V[I]}} \quad (7)$$

Where:

$$E[I] = -1/(n - 1) \quad (8)$$

$$V[I] = E[I^2] - E[I]^2 \quad (9)$$

For conceptualization of spatial relationships to specify spatial relationships among features inverse distance was opted so nearby neighbouring features have a larger influence on the computations for a target feature than features that are far away.

Euclidean Distance method was used for distance calculation from each feature to neighbouring features.

Distance threshold was determined as 102382.6104 Meters to cut off distance for the inverse distance options. Features outside the specified cutoff for a target feature are ignored in analyses for that feature.

For the Global Moran's I statistic, the null hypothesis (H_0) was stated that the residuals being analysed is randomly distributed among the features in the study area.

Results

Space Time Cube

The results of space time cube are summarised in table 1. The overall data trend direction is increasing with significant p value. Recovered and deceased cases are slightly increasing more than the confirmed cases.

The graphical representation of overall trend of confirmed cases is shown in Figure 3. The trend line shows large gap in the later half the time period, it indicate abruptly raise of the confirmed cases.

Similarly figure 4 also shows the same trend in the deceased cases. The trend is increasing at the end of the time period.

Table 1: Overall Data Trend

Confirmed Cases	
Trend direction	Increasing
Trend statistic	4.6
Trend p-value	0.0000
Recovered Cases	
Trend direction	Increasing
Trend statistic	4.7
Trend p-value	0.0000
Deceased Cases	
Trend direction	Increasing
Trend statistic	4.7
Trend p-value	0.0000

Source: <https://api.covid19india.org/>

Fig. 3: Confirmed Cases Trend

Fig. 4: Diseased Cases Trend

Emerging Hotspots for Confirmed Cases

The results of the Emerging Hotspots for Confirmed Cases are summarised in Table 2. All locations with hot spot trends are twenty two out of fifty six.

Table 2: Emerging Hotspots for Confirmed Cases

Pattern Type	Number of Hexagonal Locations		Number of Districts	
	HOT	COLD	HOT	COLD
New	14	0	22	0
Consecutive	8	0	12	0
No Pattern	34	0	41	0

Source: <https://api.covid19india.org/>

The consecutive hot spot category is the one where a single uninterrupted run of hot time step intervals, comprised of less than 90% of all intervals. The districts under consecutive hot spot category are Amethi, Bara Banki, Bhadohi, Fatehpur, Hardoi, Kanpur Dehat, Kanpur Nagar, Lucknow, Mirzapur, Rae Bareli, Sitapur, Unnao.

The new hot spot category is the one where most recent time step interval is hot for the first time. The districts under New Hot Spot are Allahabad, Azamgarh, Bijnor, Bulandshahr, Chandauli, Chitrakoot, Gautam Buddha Nagar, Ghaziabad, Ghazipur, Hapur, Jaunpur, Jyotiba Phule Nagar, Kaushambi, Mahamaya Nagar, Mathura, Mau, Meerut, Muzaffarnagar, Pratapgarh, Sambhal, Sultanpur, Varanasi. There are forty one districts shown in figure 5, where no pattern was detected.

The result shows there is no location and district where Intensifying, Persistent, Diminishing, Sporadic, Oscillating and Historical type of hot spot pattern is found in Uttar Pradesh.

Emerging Hotspots for Deceased Cases

The results of the Emerging Hotspots for deceased Cases are summarised in Table 3. All locations with hot spot trends are fifteen out of fifty six.

Fig. 5: Confirmed Cases Pattern

Table 3: Emerging Hotspots for Deceased Cases

Pattern Type	Number of Hexagonal Locations		Number of Districts	
	HOT	COLD	HOT	COLD
New	8	0	11	0
Consecutive	7	0	10	0
No Pattern	41	0	54	0

Source: <https://api.covid19india.org/>

The districts under consecutive hot spot category in case of deceased cases are Amethi, Bara Banki, Fatehpur, Hardoi, Kanpur Dehat, Kanpur Nagar, Lucknow, Rae Bareli, Sitapur, Unnao. All the districts are the same as of confirmed cases; the only exception is District Bhadoi.

The new hot spot category is the one where

Fig. 6: Deceased Cases Pattern

most recent time step interval is hot for the first time. The districts under New Hot Spot are Auraiya, Azamgarh, Bhadohi, Chandauli, Ghazipur, Hamirpur, Jalaun, Jaunpur, Kannauj, Mau, Mirzapur. The district which were found under new spot hot category in case of confirmed cases but are absent from the deceased list under the same category are Allahabad, Bijnor, Bulandshahr, Chitrakoot, Gautam Buddha Nagar, Ghaziabad, Hapur, Jyotiba Phule Nagar, Kaushambi, Mahamaya Nagar, Mathura, Mau, Meerut, Muzaffarnagar, Pratapgarh, Sambhal, Sultanpur and Varanasi. The district Jalaun is the exception as found in

the new hot spot category under deceased list but not in the confirmed list. There are forty one locations and fifty four districts shown in figure 6, where no pattern was detected.

In case of deceased category also there is no location and district where Intensifying, Persistent, Diminishing, Sporadic, Oscillating and Historical type of hot spot pattern is found in Uttar Pradesh.

Relationship between Confirmed & Diseased Cases

The results of the OLS model shows 11 districts below - 0.5 Std. Dev (standard deviation) and 11 districts above +0.5 Std. Deviation.

Table 4: No. of Districts Under Standard Residual Class

Standard residual class	No. of Districts
< -2.5 Std. Dev.	01
-2.5 - -1.5 Std. Dev.	01
-1.5 - -0.5 Std. Dev.	9
-0.5 - 0.5 Std. Dev.	53
0.5 - 1.5 Std. Dev.	10
1.5 - 2.5 Std. Dev.	0
> 2.5 Std. Dev.	1

Source: <https://api.covid19india.org/>

The above Histogram (Fig. 7) shows the residuals found as OLS result giving confirmed cases as explanatory variable and the deceased

cases as dependent variable. The histograms show how each variable is distributed. OLS does not require variables to be normally distributed.

Ideally the histogram of residuals would match the normal curve, indicated above (Fig. 7) in blue. The Histogram does not look very different from the normal curve; it indicates model is not biased. Jarque-Bera Statistic test is also not statistically significant ($p = 63.02$), so model predictions are not biased (the residuals are about to normally distributed). One bar of standard residual 6.6 is for the district Kanpur Nagar, where abnormal deceased cases are found in relation with the confirmed cases.

The scatterplot (Fig.8) depicts the relationship

Fig. 7: Histogram of Residuals

between an explanatory variable (confirmed cases) and the dependent variable (Diseased cases). Diagonal and the direction of the slant indicate that there is a strong positive relationship in between chosen variables. The point of district Lucknow shows the highest no.

of Covid confirmed cases in Uttar Pradesh but deceased cases are below the regression line. The point of Kanpur Nagar far above the regression line shows abnormally high diseased cases.

The results of the Ordinary Least Squares

Fig. 8: Diseased Cases in Relation with Confirmed Cases

(OLS) linear regression show the positive and strong relationship in between both the variables. The Coefficient of dependent (intercept) variable as 25.67 and Coefficient of independent variable as 0.01 represents the positive and strong relationship between explanatory variable and the dependent variable. The results of Probability ($p < 0.01$) and Robust Probability ($p < 0.01$) indicate coefficient is statistically significant. The Koenker (BP) Statistic test is not statistically

significant ($p = 5.244$), so the relationships modeled is consistent. Jarque-Bera Statistic test is also not statistically significant ($p = 2093.52$) so model predictions are not biased (the residuals are closed to normally distributed).

Spatial Pattern of the Residuals

Figure 9 show the p-value (0.037097) is statistically significant, and the z-score (2.084691) is positive. So, we can reject the

Fig. 9: Ordinary Least Squares Linear Regression

null hypothesis. The spatial distribution of residual's high values and/or low values in the dataset is more spatially clustered than would be expected if underlying spatial processes

were random. Given the z-score of 2.08469113983 in Table 5 confirm that there is less than 5% likelihood that this clustered pattern could be the result of random chance.

Fig. 10: Spatial Autocorrelation Graph

Table 5: Global Moran's I Summary

Moran's Index	0.084847
Expected Index:	-0.013514
Variance:	0.002226
z-score:	2.084691
p-value:	0.037097
Distance Threshold	102382.6104 Meters

Discussion

The major findings of this study are first there is overall increasing trend of the Corona – 19 cases in Uttar Pradesh. Secondly there is a significant spatial and temporal variation in the confirm and decease cases at district level in Uttar Pradesh. Thirdly there are eleven districts

which have performed well on the other hand eleven districts have not saved the life as compared to rest of the districts in the most populous state of India. The performance of the state compare to another states of India have been remarkably outstanding well.

Overall increasing trend of the Corona – 19 cases in Uttar Pradesh is mainly because the state the most populated in India.

The result of ordinary least squares demonstrates a correlation between the findings and reports published. Lucknow still has the highest number of active cases with 44,145, followed by Kanpur Nagar with 17,856, Varanasi (15,454), Prayagraj (13,186). This trend is long term but in short term reported by Chief Minister Yogi Adityanath while chairing a Covid review meeting on 12th June 2021. “The number of active Covid-19 patients has come down to 9,806, which is similar to the situation before

March end. An average of more than 2.5 to 3 lakh tests conducted daily has ensured that the cumulative positivity rate is sustained at low levels and is presently following a downward trajectory. UP's daily test positivity rate was 0.19 per cent which is one of the lowest figures in the country. The recovery rate has climbed up to 98.1 per cent,” (Express News Service, 2021).

Conclusion

The major research question answered in the present work was to find the spatial and temporal variability in term of corona conformed cases and deceased cases at district level. The research explored the potential use of space time pattern mining tool provided by ArcGIS platform for geospatial analysis. The findings will be helpful for all stockholders working to minimise the Corona problem.

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